

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF COMPLEX
METALLIC FERRO AND FERRICYANIDES. PART II.
POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION
OF COPPER FERROCYANIDE

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The composition of copper ferrocyanide has been studied by conductometric method using ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode. The composition closely approximates to $K_4Cu_2[Fe(CN)_6]_2$.

The composition of copper ferrocyanide has already been studied by the thermometric method of titration (Part I of this series, *this issue*, p. 487). In this paper use has been made of the ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode. The composition arrived at closely approximates to $K_2Cu_2[Fe(CN)_6]_2$, but is influenced by factors such as hydrolysis and adsorption.

According to the equation

the oxidation potential of the ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode is given by

$$E = E_c + 0.059 \ln \frac{[Fe(CN)_6]^{IV}}{[Fe(CN)_6]^{III}} \quad (\text{at } 25^\circ).$$

In the titration of copper sulphate solution with potassium ferrocyanide solution containing a little ferricyanide (Galetti, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1864, *is*, 2, 83; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1865, 4, 213) so long as there is an excess of copper ions in the solution, the concentration of ferrocyanide is small and so the potential of the electrode is high. As soon as the copper ions are quantitatively precipitated, the next drop of ferrocyanide solution causes a sudden increase in $[Fe(CN)_6]^{III}$, and hence a sudden decrease in the oxidation potential occurs. The equivalence point may therefore be detected.

EXPERIMENTAL

In all the titrations potassium ferrocyanide containing 1% potassium ferricyanide was used (Kolthoff-Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations"). Electrode used was of platinised platinum (Müller, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 88, 44), which was used in conjunction with the saturated calomel electrode. Graphs were plotted between $E(\text{obs.})$ against the volume of ferrocyanide added.

'Analar' (B. D. H.) reagents were used, and standard solutions were prepared as described in Part I of this series (*loc. cit.*).

M/5 solution of potassium ferrocyanide would be referred as A/1 solution and M/4.85 solution of copper sulphate, as A/1 of copper sulphate solution.

TABLE I

A/4-CuSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. (FIG. 1, curve 1).

A/2- K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)								
0.0 c.c.	0.4581 volt	3.4 c.c.	0.4031 volt	4.8 c.c.	0.3570 volt	6.2 c.c.	0.3060 volt	7.6 c.c.	0.1741 volt
1.0	0.4428	3.8	0.3919	5.0	0.3543	6.4	0.3075	7.8	0.1690
1.5	0.4347	3.8	0.3963	5.2	0.3410	6.6	0.2901	8.0	0.1649
2.0	0.4286	4.0	0.3907	5.4	0.3319	6.8	0.2816	8.5	0.1578
2.5	0.4215	4.2	0.3751	5.6	0.3278	7.0	0.2117	9.0	0.1517
3.0	0.4133	4.4	0.3700	5.8	0.3367	7.2	0.1934	9.5	0.1466
3.2	0.4087	4.6	0.3640	6.0	0.3777	7.4	0.1812	10.0	0.1425

TABLE II

A/2-CuSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. (FIG. 1, curve 2).

A/2 K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)						
0.0 c.c.	0.4581 volt	9.4 c.c.	0.3975 volt	12.0 c.c.	0.3990 volt	15.0 c.c.	0.1843 volt
1.0	0.5161	9.6	0.3924	12.2	0.3950	15.5	0.1787
2.0	0.5187	9.8	0.3864	12.4	0.3900	16.0	0.1720
3.0	0.5192	10.0	0.3797	12.6	0.3820	16.5	0.1664
4.0	0.5125	10.2	0.3706	12.8	0.3625	17.0	0.1629
5.0	0.4825	10.4	0.3634	13.0	0.3268	17.5	0.1598
6.0	0.4561	10.6	0.3532	13.2	0.2962	18.0	0.1573
7.0	0.4398	10.8	0.3431	13.4	0.2596	18.5	0.1547
7.5	0.4321	11.0	0.3340	13.6	0.2362	19.0	0.1527
8.0	0.4225	11.2	0.3324	13.8	0.2220	19.5	0.1512
8.5	0.4180	11.4	0.3349	14.0	0.2118	20.0	0.1492
9.0	0.4097	11.6	0.3461	14.2	0.2036		
9.2	0.4021	11.8	0.3628	14.5	0.1956		

TABLE III

A/10-CuSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. (FIG. 2, curve 3).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)
0.0 c.c.	0.4092 volt	4.7 c.c.	0.2698 volt	6.9 c.c.	0.1446 volt
0.5	0.3989	4.9	0.2748	7.1	0.1415
1.0	0.3807	5.0	0.3032	7.3	0.1385
1.5	0.3721	5.1	0.2667	7.5	0.1354
2.0	0.3604	5.3	0.2479	7.7	0.1344
2.5	0.3522	5.5	0.294	7.9	0.1323
3.0	0.3451	5.7	0.2898	8.1	0.1308
3.5	0.3354	5.9	0.1746	8.3	0.1293
3.7	0.3268	6.1	0.1649	8.5	0.1273
3.9	0.3207	6.3	0.1578	8.7	0.1262
4.1	0.3110	6.5	0.1527	8.9	0.1252
4.3	0.2962	6.7	0.1481	9.1	0.1237
4.5	0.2718				

TABLE IV

A/4-CuSO₄ soln. = 20 c.c. (Fig. 2, curve 4).

A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)	A/4-K ₄ FeCy ₆ added.	E(obs.)
0.0 c.c.	0.4164 volt.	10.0 c.c.	0.3527 volt.	14.0 c.c.	0.2166 volt.
1.0	0.4143	10.6	0.3344	14.2	0.2081
2.0	0.4113	11.0	0.3191	14.4	0.1929
3.0	0.4082	11.5	0.3181	14.6	0.1883
4.0	0.4042	11.7	0.3237	14.8	0.1836
5.0	0.4011	12.0	0.3431	15.0	0.1802
6.0	0.3963	12.4	0.3573	15.5	0.1710
7.0	0.3914	12.6	0.3482	16.0	0.1649
8.0	0.3848	12.8	0.3410	16.5	0.1596
8.5	0.3807	13.0	0.3280	17.0	0.1558
9.0	0.3756	13.2	0.3105	17.5	0.1527
9.2	0.3695	13.4	0.2952	18.0	0.1502
9.4	0.3644	13.6	0.2718	18.5	0.1471
9.6	0.3694	13.8	0.2372	19.0	0.1445
9.8	0.3588			19.5	0.1441
				20.0	0.1430

TABLE V

Results of the potentiometric titrations.

Curve No.	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ .	CuSO ₄ .	Obs. titre value for 20 c.c. of CuSO ₄ soln.	Equiv. vol. of K ₄ FeCy ₆ of same strength.
1	A/2	A/4	6.65 c.c.	13.30 c.c.
2	A/2	A/2	13.20	13.20
3	A/4	A/10	5.30	13.25
4	A/4	A/4	13.50	13.50

DISCUSSION

Considering the strengths of the copper sulphate (*M*/4.85) and potassium ferrocyanide (*M*/5.0) solutions, the theoretical titre values for 20 c.c. of copper sulphate solution for the formations of the compounds K₂CuFe(CN)₆, Cu₂Fe(CN)₆, and K₂Cu₂[Fe(CN)₆]₂ are 20.62, 10.31, and 13.75 c.c. respectively.

The observed titre values, which correspond to the sudden fall in potential in the latter part of the curve, are slightly lower than the theoretical ones required for the formation of the compound K₂Cu₂[Fe(CN)₆]₂. Kolthoff and Furman (*loc. cit.*), and Müller and Takagami (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1928, 73, 284) also observed that the maximum leap in potential did not occur at the required point of equivalence.

The discrepancy between the observed and the theoretical titre values can be explained on the tendency of the compound formed to hydrolyse. The phenomenon of hydrolysis has already been shown to play an important role in the precipitation of this compound (Part I of this series). Then potassium ferrocyanide, thus released, will react with some copper sulphate solution, with the result that the observed titre values would be lower than the theoretical values required.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The adsorption of copper ions by copper ferrocyanide sol has also been observed. This would also tend to lower the titre value. It seems that these facts were not taken into consideration by Kolthoff and Furman, and by Müller and Takagami.

In the loop obtained in the first part of the curve, the first decrease in E. M. F. is evidently due to the increase in concentration of the $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ ions, released by copper ferrocyanide. The latter portion *i.e.* the rise in the curve is probably due to the adsorption of the $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ ions from the solution.

The titrations could not be followed in the presence of alcohol (*vide* Part I of the series) as constant values of potential could not be obtained to assure reproducibility of results. It is, however, difficult to explain with certainty the actual cause of similar loops which appear in each titration curve. Hydrolysis and adsorption phenomena disturbing the equilibrium of the ratio of

$$\frac{[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}]^m}{[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}]^{14}}$$

seem to be responsible for this observation.

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